

**PUPILS' RESILIENCY IN THE NEW LEARNING RECOVERY
PROGRAM OF THE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION:
AS PERCEIVED BY THE TEACHERS**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 9

Pages: 1038-1043

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14843399

Manuscript Accepted: 10-14-2024

Pupils' Resiliency in the New Learning Recovery Program of the Department of Education: As Perceived by the Teachers

Junerose O. Damiles,* Marilou M. Rodriguez
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study attempted to determine the pupils' resiliency in the new learning recovery program and its implication to pupils' school performance. It also ascertains the extent of pupils' resiliency in terms of academic and personal resiliency, the level of pupils' academic performance, and ascertain the significant relationship between the level of pupils' academic performance and the extent of pupils' resiliency. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized, and the Statistical tools used in the study were mean, frequency count, standard deviation, percentages to analyze the extent of pupils' resiliency, level of pupils' academic performance, Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the level of pupils' academic performance and the extent of pupils' resiliency. Findings revealed that pupils had "Very High" extent of academic and personal resiliency, pupils with academic and personal resilience performed fairly in their academic performance. Statistically, academic and personal resilience signify moderate correlation to pupils' academic performance. Subsequently, it was recommended that in order to intensify pupils' academic and personal resiliency, teachers should provide classroom performance tasks that intensify or enhance resiliency in order to withstand to different challenging learning situations.

Keywords: *pupils' resiliency, academic and personal resiliency, academic performance, learning recovery program*

Introduction

Education has an alleviating significance on learners in times of quandaries and helps them develop resiliency in facing challenges. It is imperative for education to continue and brings a sense of normalcy that softens the blow of vulnerability in times of disorder.

The implementation of the learning recovery plan (LRP) prepares students to catch up after the two years of disruption due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The learning recovery plan aims not only to bring learners back to school but to organize effective remedial learning, support their well-being and train teachers, for the classes for the school year 2022 – 2023. Additionally, the learning recovery plan will give more attention to the literacy and numeracy skills of the learners who were affected by lockdowns and self-learning approach during the pandemic.

The framework of the study is bounded on the context of legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to RM 395, series of 2022 also known as the school learning recovery and continuity plan for public and private schools for the school year 2022-2023 to 2023-2024. The learning recovery plan aims to ensure that learners across grade levels can catch up and accelerate their learning. moreover, the framework intends to address socio-emotional and behavioural recovery of learners.

The learning recovery plan allows pupils to move forward in the challenging times, the education sector needs to demonstrate resilience the ability to overcome adversity, a lifelong skill that it purports to develop among learners. In school, staying resilient can mean finding opportunities amidst the challenge. For pupils within the school, it can mean thriving despite difficult circumstances (Estrada, 2022).

Further, it was emphasized that the learning recovery plan stimulates pupils to learn and grow in all situations and learning skills that are crucial to well-being and development. Resilience will also help pupils to approach new situations, experiences with confidence and a positive mindset, which will make them more likely to succeed.

Alban (2021) asserted that pupils' resiliency can help protect them from various mental health conditions, such as depression and anxiety. Resilience can also help offset factors that increase the risk of mental health conditions, such as being bullied or previous trauma. Further, resilient students sustain high levels of achievement motivation and performance despite the presence of stressful events and conditions that place them at risk of doing poorly in school and ultimately dropping out of school.

Subsequently, Galante, et al (2021) pointed out that the purpose of school learning recovery plan incorporates the support and enabling mechanisms that shall be established and operationalized to ensure efficiency and effectiveness in learning delivery to address the learning gaps, improve learning outcomes, and the total well-being of the learners.

However, Morales, et al (2022) indicated that pupils with higher academic resilience had higher probabilities of maintaining and improving academic and school performance compared to other students. Additionally, the implementation of face-to-face classes of the Department of Education resulted to overwhelming challenges to teachers especially on pupils' learning behaviour which affect their academic and school performance.

Subsequently, it was asserted that public schools should be encouraged to make policies that help intensify pupils' academic resiliency not only during pandemic but also during the post-pandemic and the learning recovery phase in education as well as examine the risks

and protective factors during the implementation of the learning recovery program.

It is based on the above-stated considerations that the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to ascertain the pupils' resiliency in the implementation of the learning recovery program of the Department of Education and how this affect pupils' school performance especially in Lumbia Central School in the City of Division of Cagayan de Oro for the school year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the influence of pupils' resiliency in the implementation of the new learning recovery program and its implication to pupils' school performance. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do teachers assess pupils' resiliency in the implementation of the new learning recovery program in terms of the following components:
 - 1.1. academic; and
 - 1.2. personal?
2. How do teachers assess pupils' school performance in terms of the following category:
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. fairly satisfactory; and,
 - 2.5. did not meet expectation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the pupils' resiliency in the implementation of the new learning recovery program and pupils' school performance?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of survey questionnaires, interview, and focused-group discussion (FGD).

Instrument

This study adapted the research of Estrada (2022) who asserted that pupils with high academic resiliency can immediately overcome adversities and educational challenges and can perform effectively in their academic and school performance.

The survey instrument is composed of two (2) major components. The first component is on pupils' resiliency in terms of the following category; namely, academic and personal resiliency. Each of the category will be composed of ten (10) indicators.

Additionally, the second component of the survey questionnaire is on the pupils' school performance which will be described as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

The same permission was asked by the researcher to the parents of the pupil-respondents to participate in the study and allow the former to use pupils' school performance in terms of grades as the variable of this study. Moreover, the parents were assured that the data gathered be treated to its highest confidentiality and for research purposes only.

After the observation of pupil-respondents and interview, the researcher summarized and tabulated the data and submitted to the Statistician for analysis using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment are utilized to answer the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of pupils' resiliency in terms of academic and personal resiliency.

For Problem 2, frequency and percentages were used to present the pupils' school performance.

For Problem 3, Pearson-r was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the pupils' resiliency and their school performance.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on pupils' resiliency in the new learning recovery program and its implication to pupils' school performance. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the results of a survey questionnaire in lieu of the problems presented.

Problem 1. How do teachers assess pupils' resiliency in the implementation of the new learning recovery program in terms of the following components: Academic and Personal?

The learning recovery program was adopted by the Department of Education to address the gaps among students and that were heightened by distance learning modality. The primary purpose of learning recovery plan is a process of change through which learners improve their learning performance and school participation.

The learning recovery plan aims not only to bring learners back to school but to organize effective remedial learning, support their well-being and train teachers to address new challenges in teaching. Additionally, the learning recovery plan will give more attention to the literacy and numeracy skills of the learners who were affected by lockdowns and self-learning approach during the pandemic.

Table 1.1 presents the mean distribution of pupils' learning recovery program in terms of academic resiliency.

Table 1.1. Mean Distribution of Pupils' Learning Recovery Program in terms of Academic Resiliency

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Pupil manages their learning activities	3.98	1.067	High Extent
2. Pupil engages in class and group works.	4.06	1.000	High Extent
3. Pupil communicates well to ensure class participation	4.05	.917	High Extent
4. Pupil interacts with classmates and teachers to improve learning	3.99	.912	High Extent
5. Pupil thinks independently and makes decisions according to situations or conditions	4.02	1.611	High Extent
6. Pupil thinks reflectively and creatively	3.96	2.361	High Extent
7. Pupil manifests interest and enthusiasm to learn	3.71	.906	High Extent
8. Pupil demonstrates excellent behavior	3.60	.983	High Extent
9. Pupil adapts easily to any learning situations and conditions	3.49	1.095	High Extent
10. Pupil works well even in changing and challenging environment	3.39	1.216	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	3.83	1.207	High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of pupils' learning recovery program in terms of academic resiliency. Overall, the respondents rated academic resiliency as "High Extent" with a mean of 3.83 (SD=1.207). This result indicates that higher importance was given on academic learning and mastery of basic competencies in every learning area during the implementation of the learning recovery program. Additionally, academic resiliency emphasized on pupils achieving good educational outcomes despite of the adversities.

Carillo and Flores (2022) avowed that academic resilience in the learning recovery program highlights on students achieving good learning outcomes amidst the various difficulties and challenges they experienced. The school has to strategically plan the detailed activities in developing pupils' resiliency in their academic and learning activities.

The indicator "Pupil engages in class and group works" obtained the highest mean value of 4.06 (SD= 1.000) which is verbally described as "High Extent" which indicates that teachers encourage pupils' engagement in class and group activities and performance tasks in order to allow them to interact, collaborate, and participate in group work class activities.

This finding was supported by Padilla, et al (2022) who pointed out that pupils' resiliency to the new learning recovery program is developed through practical engagements in work-related activities in order for the pupils to withstand and easily recover from their previous debauched experiences.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.39 (SD=1.216) is verbally described as "Moderate Extent" in the indicator "Pupil works well even if changing and challenging environment". The result implies that teachers sensibly and reasonably provide performance tasks to pupils in order to adjust the changing and challenging work settings.

This finding was supported by Estrada (2022) who espoused that pupils' exposure to changing and challenging environment helps enhance resiliency because exposure to challenging learning environment stimulates pupils to learn and grow in all situations as it is crucial to well-being and development. Resilience will also help pupils to approach new situations, experiences with confidence and a

positive mindset, which will make them more likely to succeed.

Table 1.2. Mean Distribution of Pupils’ Learning Recovery Program in terms of Personal Resiliency

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Pupil develops personal adaptability to teachers.	4.44	.873	Very High Extent
2. Pupil collaborates and work with peers and classmates.	4.51	.801	Very High Extent
3. Pupil manifests flexibility in working with diverse learners.	4.48	.780	Very High Extent
4. Pupil copes and adapts to new learning environment.	4.46	.779	Very High Extent
5. Pupil manifests maturity and independence	4.36	.831	Very High Extent
6. Pupil manifests personal motivation to learn	4.22	.866	Very High Extent
7. Pupil shows personal interest in learning	4.01	.865	High Extent
8. Pupil develops social-interact skills with classmates.	3.71	1.032	High Extent
9. Pupil stimulates and motivates others to participate in class	3.61	1.140	High Extent
10. Pupil forges social interactions with teachers and fellow learners	3.55	1.278	High Extent
Overall Mean	4.14	.925	High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1.2 displays the mean distribution of pupils’ learning recovery program in terms of personal resiliency. Overall, the respondents rated personal resiliency as “High Extent” with a mean of 4.14 (SD=.925). This result indicates that great importance was given on personal recovery during the implementation of learning recovery.

Personal resilience involves behaviors, thoughts, and actions that promote personal wellbeing and mental health. Teachers with higher personal resiliency can develop their ability to withstand, adapt to, and recover from stress and adversity and maintain or return to a state of mental health wellbeing by using effective coping strategies.

Carillo and Flores (2022) averred that teachers with higher personal resilience can build strong, healthy relationships with the teachers within the school organization, can give needed support and help guide them overcome challenges.

The indicator “Pupil collaborates and work with peers and classmates” obtained the highest mean value of 4.51 (SD= .801) which is verbally described as “Very High Extent” which indicates that teachers encourage pupils to collaborates and work with their peers and classmates. It can be inferred based on findings that pupils with higher engagement in class and group activities are stimulated by teachers with higher personal resilience.

This finding was supported by Padilla, et al (2022) who pointed out that teachers with higher personal resiliency to the new learning recovery program is developed through practical engagements in work-related activities in order for the pupils to withstand and easily recover from their previous debauched experiences.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.55 (SD=1.278) is verbally described as “High Extent” in the indicator “Pupil forges social interactions with teachers and fellow learners”. The result implies that students greatly judiciously forge social interactions with teachers and fellow learners and can easily relate and understand varying degree of social interactions.

This finding was supported by Estrada (2022) who espoused that students with tremendous extent of personal resiliency can easily forge interactions and develop certain degree of group interaction skills.

Problem 2. How do teachers assess pupils’ school performance in terms of the following category: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectations?

Pupils’ school performance success through learning performance is predictive of pupils’ motivation to learn and master the learning competencies which is translated into numerical data or grades categorized as Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Pupils’ Academic Performance

Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	0	0
Very Satisfactory	0	0
Satisfactory	20	20%
Fairly Satisfactory	55	55%
Did not meet expectations	25	25
Total	100	100%

It can be asserted that out of 100 respondents, 55 (55%) had a “Fairly Satisfactory” academic performance while only 20 or 20% of the respondents had a “Satisfactory” academic performance. This indicates that majority of the respondents performed equitably and justifiably in their academic activities. It can be inferred based on findings that pupils perform justifiably in their academic activities during the learning recovery program. This finding was supported by Murphy and Hallinger (2020) who exemplified that pupils’ performance declines during the recovery period because of some resiliency concerns. Pupils who did not achieve certain level of

personal resiliency cannot perform effectively in their learning performance.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the pupils' resiliency in the implementation of the new learning recovery program and pupils' school performance?

Table 3 presents the test of relationship between the pupils' resiliency in the implementation of the new learning recovery program and pupils' school performance.

Table 3. Test of Relationship between Pupils' Resiliency and Pupils' Academic Performance

<i>Pupils' Resiliency</i>	<i>Pupils' Academic Performance</i>			
	<i>(rs)</i>	<i>Probability Value Sig. (2 tailed)</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision on Ho1</i>
Academic Resiliency	.642	.000	Signifies moderate correlation	Rejected
Personal Resiliency	.688	.000	Signifies moderate correlation	Rejected

**significant at p<0.05 alpha level*

Table 3 displays the results of the test of relationship between pupils' resiliency and the implementation of new learning recovery program and pupils' academic performance. Results revealed that pupils' academic resiliency signifies "Moderate Correlation" to pupils' academic performance ($rs=.642$) as indicated in the probability value of .000. This result indicates that pupils' academic performance was influenced by their academic resiliency. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Moreover, results recommended that pupils' personal resiliency signifies "Moderate Correlation" to pupils' academic performance ($rs=.688$) as indicated in probability value of .000. This result implies that pupils' academic performance was influenced by their personal resiliency. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

As a summary, pupils' academic and personal resiliencies are factors that affect the level of pupils' academic performance which means that the more resilient the pupils in the new learning recovery program, the better they can perform their school activities and improve their academic performance.

These findings were support by Simons, et al (2022) who posited that pupils' resiliency encompasses diversity, connectivity, feedback and encouraging learning. It was also highlighted that pupils' academic and personal resiliency creates positive effects in cognitive reappraisal and social support which predict pupils' ability to cope with the challenges in new learning recovery program. Further, Theron (2023) puts it, resilience is focused on a range of factors at a macro level in terms of pupils and educational institution. Pupils' resiliency is intensified when the educational institution through teaches provide the supportive climate, networks, peer support, and resilient school environment.

The pupils' resiliency with respect to the new learning recovery program was explored by Simons, et al (2022) as internal challenges to managing studies, persistence factors such as teachers' feedback, motivation and self-belief, support to pupils, pupil-pupil relationships, friends, and family are relevant in developing pupils' resiliency to the in-person learning modality.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The learning recovery program aims to strengthen the learning recovery and continuing program, improves literacy and numeracy, and accelerate the achievement of education targets. The learning recovery program allows pupils to learn and apply study skills to organize and learn a large amount of information in a new setting and learning style.

Pupils' academic performance is the measurement of pupils' achievement across various academic subjects. Teachers and education officials typically measure achievement using classroom performance. Another factor of pupils' academic performance is pupils' academic and personal resiliency to withstand any challenges in school and in learning.

Pupils' resiliency enables them to cope with the challenges, obstacles, and setbacks they are likely to experience on their learning. Academic and personal resiliency affect favorably pupils' academic and learning performance. Resiliency allows them to learn and grow in all situations. It will also help them to approach new situations, people or experiences with confidence and a positive pupils' mindset which will make them more likely to succeed in their academic endeavor.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will provide school heads and teachers the framework for an intensified resiliency program to help pupils adjust and withstand challenging situations.

School Principals/School Heads will recommend teachers to provide class activities which strengthens pupils' resiliency to withstand in different learning challenges.

Teachers are recommended to continuously develop and enhance their skills in developing pupils' academic and personal resiliency in order to withstand to any challenging academic situations.

Parents are recommended to always provide the needed support in their children's learning activities and at the same time provide support in developing their child's resiliency to adjust and withstand in any challenging situations.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders are recommended to always support and provide logistical assistance to the school especially in the utilization of information and communication technology resources which help support especially in intensifying pupils' resiliency.

Future Researchers are encouraged to conduct a similar study on pupils' resiliency and other strategies to enhance pupils' ability to withstand in any type of challenging experiences and how resiliency help improve pupils' academic performance.

References

- Alban, C. (2021). Student resilience after pandemic: Learning loss recovery. *International Journal of Educational Development*, Volume 1, No.2, Page 1-10
- Appolloni, A., Colasanti, N., Fantauzzi, C., Fiorani, G., and Frondizi, R. (2021). Distance Learning as a Resilience Strategy during Covid-19: An Analysis of the Italian Context. *Sustainability* 13 (3), 1388.
- Beale, J. (2020). Academic Resilience and its Importance in Education after Covid-19. *Eton J. Innov. Res. Educ.* 4, 1–6.
- Briggs, T., et al (2021). *Principles of building resilience: Sustaining ecosystem services in social-ecological systems*. Arizona. Cambridge University Press.
- Carillo, C. and Flores, M. (2022). *Resiliency and learning recovery program*. Teaching and Learning Practice. McGraw Publication.
- Estrada, R. (2022). Mindfulness, resilience, emotional exhaustion, and turnover intention in secondary physical education teaching. *European Review Applied Psychology*.
- Fullerton, D. J., Zhang, L. M., and Kleitman, S. (2021). An Integrative Process Model of Resilience in an Academic Context: Resilience Resources, Coping Strategies, and Positive Adaptation. *Plos One* 16, e0246000.
- Galante, A., et al (2021). A mindfulness-based intervention to increase resilience to stress: A pragmatic randomized controlled trial. *Lancet Public Health*.
- Manca, A. R. (2022). Time for Transformative Resilience: the COVID-19 Emergency. *JRC Working Papers*, No. JRC120489. Joint Research Centre-Seville site.
- Marciano, H., Eshel, Y., and Adini, B. (2021). Recovery from the COVID-19 Pandemic: Distress and Resilience. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.* 50, 101843.
- Morales-Rodríguez, F. M., Martínez-Ramón, J. P., Méndez, I., Ruiz-Esteban, C., and Ruiz-Esteban, C. (2022). Stress, Coping, and Resilience before and after COVID-19: A Predictive Model Based on Artificial Intelligence in the university Environment. *Front. Psychol.* 12, 647964.
- Nandy, M., Lodh, S., and Tang, A. (2022). Lessons from COVID-19 and a Resilience Model for Higher Education. *Ind. High. Edu.* 35, 3–9.
- Padilla, A., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., Mercader, I., López-Liria, R., and Rocamora, P. (2022). The Influence of Transformational Teacher Leadership on Academic Motivation and Resilience, Burnout and Academic Performance. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 1720, 7687.
- Ramos, J. and Holland, K. (2022). What factors promote student resilience on level 1 learning recovery program. *Recovery Learning Journal*, 33, 14-17
- Sánchez Ruiz, L. M., Moll-López, S., Moraño-Fernández, J. A., Llobregat-Gómez, N., and Llobregat-Gómez, J. A. (2021). B-learning and Technology: Enablers for university Education Resilience. *Sustainability* 136, 3532.
- Theron, L. (2021). *Learning about systemic resilience from studies of student resilience. Adaptation and transformation in contexts of change*. Oxford University Press, 232-252.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Junerose O. Damiles

St. Peter's College – Philippines

Marilou M. Rodriguez, PhD

St. Peter's College – Philippines